

Photons of Mobile waves could cause some delays in transmission information between spinors within the heart, hemoglobin molecules and cells.

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Abstract: Biological systems like the heart, hemoglobin and cells are built from entangled spinors. Entangled spinors exchange information through two ways: 1. Spinor waves with the velocity of infinity. 2. Photons with the limited velocity. If any spin in a pair reverses, other spin changes immediately. However, initial exchanged photons don't understand these changes and have the memory of previous stage. Thus, when they reach the spinors, repel them. By passing time, new emitted photons from spinors obtain the true information and absorb other spinors in a pair. These repelling and absorbing causes to oscillation of heart cells and motions of blood cells including hemoglobin. These molecules transmit information and oxygen and give them to cells. A mobile wave could break entanglements between spinors of hemoglobins, cause to a delay in information and oxygen transmission from heart to some cells and creating non-normal cells like tumor ones. Because, without information, cells have to act independent of other cells. Also, without oxygen, cells have to use of other mechanisms for respiration like the ones which used by tumor cells in the Warburg proposal. This is not depended on the wavelength. Because, wavelength only determines probability of existence of photons in each point and waves with any wavelength (even bigger than cell size) is formed from many photons with smaller size respect to cells. Although, by passing time after establishing electromagnetic towers, spinor structure of body could be resistance in front of these waves and the probability for the emergence of tumors decreases. Without this resistance and according to the Warburg proposal, generated tumor cells produce different number of spinors which help them to diagnose the motions of T-cells and become ready to response. To avoid this event, we may use again of some mobile waves which produce some noises around tumor cells.

Keywords: Mobile waves; Tumors; Hemoglobin; Heart; Spinors

I. Introduction:

Recent investigations have shown that mobile waves have very dangerous effects on biological cells. For example, some investigators have described that

radiofrequency radiation (RFR) emitted from mobile phones has a potential to produce DNA damage in follicle cells of hair in the ear canal [1]. Some other authors have argued that 5G mobile networking technology will affect not only the skin and eyes, but will have adverse systemic effects as well [2]. Another study has investigated the non-thermal effects of Wi-Fi radiofrequency radiation of 2.4 GHz on global gene expression in *Escherichia coli* K-12 DH5 α . According to its results, the exposure of *E. coli* DH5 α to Wi-Fi radiofrequency radiation for 5 hours influenced several bacterial cellular and metabolic processes [3]. Another paper has proposed some evidences for a connection between coronavirus disease-19 and exposure to radiofrequency radiation from wireless communications including 5G [4]. Another research has indicated that 900-, 1800-, and 2100-MHz waves emitted from mobile phones may cause oxidative damage, induce increase in lipid peroxidation, and increase oxidative DNA damage formation in the frontal lobe of the rat brain tissues. Furthermore, 2100-MHz RFR may cause formation of DNA single-strand breaks [5]. Another article has evaluated 18 studies that included 4280 samples and showed that mobile phone usage is harmful to sperm quality [6]. Another work has considered the effects of RF exposure from mobile phone on human brainwaves, which can provide information about the mental state of the individual [7]. Another investigation has discussed that scrotal hyperthermia and increased oxidative stress might be the key mechanisms through which electromagnetic waves affect male fertility. However, these negative effects appear to be associated with the duration of mobile phone use [8]. Motivated by these researches, we propose a model which shows how mobile waves could break entanglement between biological spinors of hemoglobins, heart and cells and cause to a decrease in information transmissions from heart to normal cells. This information lost may cause to the emergence of some diseases like cancers.

The outline of paper is as follows: In section II, we will describe the model and consider the effects of mobile waves on biological spinors within the hemoglobin and heart. In section III, we propose the mathematical results. The last sections devoted to discussion and conclusion.

II. The model: Considering interactions between biological spinors and mobile waves

Recently, some scientists have announced that mobile waves could have harmful effects on biological cells and even cause to hard diseases like cancers. However

factories response that wavelengths of mobile waves are bigger than the size of cells and have no effects on them. There is a mistake in understanding the quantum concept of wavelengths and waves. A wave is formed from many photons which their sizes are very smaller than the size of cells. A wavelength is a quantity which determines the probability for the existence of a photon in one point. For example, when a peak of a wavelength is placed at one point, there is more probability for finding a photon there; while in other points of a wavelength, this probability is smaller. Thus, even radio waves with large wavelengths are built of photons with small sizes which could pass the cell membranes and reach the DNA. However, number of photons which in each time collide with biological cells, increases with the reductions of wavelengths. Because, by reducing the wavelength, the separation distances between peaks decreases and if one supposes that each peak includes a photon, number of photons increases (See figure 1).

Now, the question arises that how photons of mobile waves interact with biological cells. To response this question, we should remember that the biological structures like hearts, hemoglobin molecules and cells are built from spinors like electrons and atoms. These spinors could interact with any external wave like mobile waves. To describe these interactions, first we should consider the process of information transmission from the heart spinors to hemoglobin ones and cells. These spinors are entangled and exchange information through two ways: 1. Spinor waves which move with the velocity of infinity. This means that in an entangled system, when a spin changes, all spins change immediately. 2. Photons which move with the limited velocity like the velocity of light (See Figure 2).

To clear the role of these waves in blood circularly systems, we consider two spinors in a pair. These spinors emit photons which move from a spin to other one. If a spin in this pair reverses, other spin could reverse immediately. However, exchanged photons have the memory of initial state and when become close to any spinor, repel it. By passing time, new photons are emitted by spinors which have true information. When these photons become close to any spinor in this pair attract it. This repelling and attraction causes to an oscillation of spinors. The same event occurs within the heart. A difference between time of information transmissions by spinor waves and photons causes to the oscillation of heart cells and motions of blood cells (See Figure 3). Red blood cells include hemoglobin molecules which contain iron atoms and many spinors. Iron atoms could play the

role of antenna, take information from heart cells or brain ones and store them. Then, they move within vessels and give these information to biological cells. Spinors of heart, hemoglobin molecules and cells are entangled. Any change in spinors around a cell could be diagnosed by other cells immediately (See Figure 4). However, these entanglement may be decreased by external waves. For example, mobile waves could divide into photons. These photons break the entanglement between spinors of hemoglobin molecules and produce new entanglements between these spinors and spinors on tower or mobile antenna (See Figure 5). By decreasing entanglement between biological spinors, information couldn't be transformed between cells and some cells lose information. Maybe, these cells do their activities without knowing states of other cells and independent of them. Also, maybe, some hemoglobin molecules couldn't provide needed oxygen for these cells. Consequently, without information and oxygen, these cells may use of respirational methods which are using by tumor cells in the Warburg proposal [9,10]. This may causes to the cancer (See Figure 6). According to the Warburg idea [9-12], products of cancer cells are different from normal ones. For example, normal cells take oxygen and glucose and give water, carbon dioxide, ATP and spinors; while tumor cells take glucose and give lactate and different numbers of spinors respect to normal cells (See Figure 7). This change in number of spinors cause to a change in entangled biological system and can be diagnosed by T-cells. These cells move and their motions change the spins of system. These new changes in spinors could be understood by tumor cells and they become ready to response to attack of T-cells by producing harmful connections like PD1/PD-L1 ones. To avoid of these connections, we can use of mobile waves and induce some extra photons around tumor cells. These photons act like the noise and cause to the information lost. Consequently, tumor cells couldn't understand the existence of T-cells and these cells have the opportunity to kill tumor cells (See Figure 8).

Wave Length \neq Size of Photon

Wave length is only a prediction of the existence of photons on the peaks not their sizes

Each wave is a train of photon packages

Figure 1. Differences between quantum concepts of wavelengths and the size of photons

Figure 2. Exchanged spinor waves and photons between spinors.

Figure 3. A difference between time of information transmission by spinor waves and photon cause to the oscillation of heart cells and motions of blood cells.

Figure 4: Hemoglobin molecules which are located on red cells take information from the heart and some cells, move along vessels and give them to other cells.

Figure 5. A decrease in quantum entanglements between spinors of hemoglobin molecules by electromagnetic waves

Figure 6. Extra electromagnetic waves like mobile one decrease entanglement between biological spins and cause to lose of information around cells.

Figure 7. The Warburg effect. Differences between products of normal and tumor cells.

Figure 8. Inducing noises around tumor cells by using mobile waves

III. Mathematical results:

In this section, we will calculate the needed time for transformation of information between biological spinors. It has been known that within an entangled system of two spinors, states could be:

$$|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle \text{ or } |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle \quad (1)$$

When, the arrow of one spin changes, the arrow of other spinor changes immediately. This is because that spinor waves move with the velocity of infinity. In fact, we write a general wave function as below:

$$|ES, 2\rangle = \cos(\alpha_{T,EM}) |\uparrow\downarrow\rangle + \sin(\alpha_{T,EM}) |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle \quad (2)$$

Where $|ES\rangle$ is the function of entangled spinors, T is temperature of medium in that point and EM is the index related to electromagnetic waves. The probability for each state can be obtained from below equations:

$$P_{|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle} = \cos^2(\alpha_{T,EM})$$

$$P_{|\downarrow\uparrow\rangle} = \sin^2(\alpha_{T,EM}) \quad (3)$$

Above probabilities depend on the temperature of medium and external electromagnetic waves. Summing over probabilities should be equal to one:

$$P_{|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle} + P_{|\downarrow\uparrow\rangle} = 1 \quad (4)$$

We can rewrite equation (2) as follows:

$$|ES, 2\rangle = \sum_{i,j=0,1} \sqrt{P_{ij}} |ij\rangle$$

$$P_{ii} = P_{jj} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Where $i,j=0$ corresponds to spin (\uparrow) and $i,j=1$ corresponds to spin (\downarrow).

In a biological system, each of spinors may be entangled by more spinors. For example, for four entangled spinors, we have:

$$|ES, 4\rangle = \sum \sqrt{P_{ijkl}} |ij\otimes kl\rangle$$

$$P_{iiii} = P_{jjjj} = P_{kkkk} = P_{llll} = 0 \quad (6)$$

And for N spinors, we have:

$$|ES, N\rangle = \prod_{n=1}^N \sum_{i_1 \dots i_n} \sqrt{P_{i_1 \dots i_n}} |i_1 i_2 \otimes \dots \otimes i_{n-1} i_n\rangle$$

$$P_{\dots i_1 i_1 \dots} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Where the probability for similar spinors which are near each other is zero.

These spinors exchange two types of waves:

1. Spinor waves which their velocities are infinite. For example, when a spin in this entangled spin changes all spinors change immediately. We can write:

$$t_{spinor-wave} = 0 \quad (8)$$

2. Photonic waves which their velocities are limited. In a flat space-time, the velocity of photons is :

$$V_{photon-flat} = c = 3 \times 10^8 \quad (9)$$

However, spinors produce some magnetic fields. These magnetic fields force particles and cause to their accelerations. According to Unruh effect, this acceleration change the space-time and velocity of photons [13,14]. First, we can obtain the magnetic field of this system

$$B_{TOT} \rightarrow S_{TOT} \quad (10)$$

Where B is the magnetic field and S is the spin. Above equation shows that the magnetic field of a system has a direct relation with its spin. For biological entangled spinors, we can write:

$$B_{TOT} \rightarrow S_{TOT} \rightarrow \prod_{n=1}^N \sum_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \sqrt{P_{i_1, \dots, i_n}} [S_{i_1, \dots, i_n}]$$

$$S_{i_1, \dots, i_n} = S_{i_1} + \dots + S_{i_n} \quad (11)$$

This magnetic field could produce the energy density. For n spinors between two red blood cells and their hemoglobin molecules, we can write:

$$U_{i_1, \dots, i_n} = \frac{[B_{i_1, \dots, i_n}]^2}{2\mu_0} = \frac{\lambda_{i_1, \dots, i_n} [S_{i_1} + \dots + S_{i_n}]^2}{2\mu_0} \quad (12)$$

Where $\lambda_{i_1, \dots, i_n}$ is a parameter which relates the magnetic field to the spin. Suppose that spinors on two blood cells oscillate. We can write:

$$E_{i_1, \dots, i_n} = U_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \pi (R_{cell} + x)^2 l_n \quad (13)$$

Where R_{cell} is the radius of cell, x is the oscillation parameter and l_n is the separation distances between two cells. Taking derivatives respect to above equation gives:

$$F_{i_1, \dots, i_n} = \frac{d E_{i_1, \dots, i_n}}{dx} = 2U_{i_1, \dots, i_n} \pi (R_{cell} + x) l_n \quad (14)$$

To calculate the acceleration, we can ignore the oscillation parameter and write:

$$a_{i_1 \dots i_n} = \frac{F_{i_1 \dots i_n}}{n m_{electron}} = \frac{2U_{i_1 \dots i_n} \pi (R_{cell}) l_n}{n m_{electron}} \quad (15)$$

Where $a_{i_1 \dots i_n}$ is the acceleration of spinors and $m_{electron}$ is the electron mass.

This acceleration produces a Unruh temperature (14):

$$T_{i_1 \dots i_n} = \frac{a_{i_1 \dots i_n}}{2\pi} \quad (16)$$

Where $T_{i_1 \dots i_n}$ is the Unruh temperature in this point. In this temperature, some photons are produced that their states, could be obtained from below equation:

$$|photon, T_{i_1 \dots i_n}, E_{Photon, i_1 \dots i_n}\rangle = \frac{1}{\cosh r_{T_{i_1 \dots i_n}}} \sum_m^M \tanh^m r_{T_{i_1 \dots i_n}} |m \uparrow \uparrow, I\rangle |m \downarrow \downarrow, II\rangle \quad (17)$$

Where $|photon, T_{i_1 \dots i_n}\rangle$ is the photonic wave function, m is the number of exchanged photons, I denotes the region I and II denotes the region II of curved space-time.

Also, we have:

$$\tanh r_{T_{i_1 \dots i_n}} = \exp\left(-\frac{E_{Photon, i_1 \dots i_n}}{T_{i_1 \dots i_n}}\right) \quad (18)$$

Where $E_{Photon, i_1 \dots i_n}$ is the photonic energy. The probability for producing m photons can be obtained from below equation:

$$P_m = \left[\frac{\tanh^m r_{T_{i_1 \dots i_n}}}{\cosh r_{T_{i_1 \dots i_n}}}\right]^2 \quad (19)$$

This probability isn't complete and we should regard the probability of entangled spinors so:

$$P_{m, |photon, T_{i_1 \dots i_n}\rangle} = \prod_{n=1}^N \sum_{i_1 \dots i_n} \sqrt{P_{i_1 \dots i_n}} [P_m] = \prod_{n=1}^N \sum_{i_1 \dots i_n} \sqrt{P_{i_1 \dots i_n}} \left[\frac{\tanh^m r_{T_{i_1 \dots i_n}}}{\cosh r_{T_{i_1 \dots i_n}}}\right]^2 \quad (20)$$

Total energy of photons in this point, can be obtained by multiplying the probability of equation (20) and photonic energies:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{E}_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n} &= \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{E_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n}}{m} P_{m,|photon,r_{T_{i_1\dots i_n}}\rangle} = \\
&\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{E_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n}}{m} \prod_{n=1}^N \sum_{i_1\dots i_n} \sqrt{P_{i_1\dots i_n}} [P_m] = \\
&\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{E_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n}}{m} \prod_{n=1}^N \sum_{i_1\dots i_n} \sqrt{P_{i_1\dots i_n}} \left[\left[\frac{\tanh^m r_{T_{i_1\dots i_n}}}{\cosh r_{T_{i_1\dots i_n}}} \right]^2 \right] \quad (22)
\end{aligned}$$

Above photonic energy could help us to obtain the period of time:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{E}_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n} &= h\nu_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n} \rightarrow \nu_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n} = \frac{\hat{E}_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n}}{h} \\
t_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n} &= \frac{1}{\nu_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n}} \rightarrow t_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n} = \frac{h}{\hat{E}_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n}} \\
\rightarrow t_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n} &= h \left[\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{E_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n}}{m} \prod_{n=1}^N \sum_{i_1\dots i_n} \sqrt{P_{i_1\dots i_n}} \left[\left[\frac{\tanh^m r_{T_{i_1\dots i_n}}}{\cosh r_{T_{i_1\dots i_n}}} \right]^2 \right] \right]^{-1} \quad (23)
\end{aligned}$$

Where $\nu_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n}$ is the frequency, h is the plank constant and $t_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n}$ is the period time of photons. This time depends on the spinor structures of system, number of spinors in that point, magnetic fields, separation between molecules and accelerations. Total time which lasts that some informations are transmitted from spin 1 in point 1 for example a point on the heart to spin N for example a point on a cell could be obtained by summing over all times:

$$\begin{aligned}
t_{Photon,information,N} &= \sum_{n=1}^N t_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n} \\
&= \sum_{n=1}^N h \left[\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{E_{Photon,i_1\dots i_n}}{m} \prod_{n=1}^N \sum_{i_1\dots i_n} \sqrt{P_{i_1\dots i_n}} \left[\left[\frac{\tanh^m r_{T_{i_1\dots i_n}}}{\cosh r_{T_{i_1\dots i_n}}} \right]^2 \right] \right]^{-1} \quad (24)
\end{aligned}$$

Above equation shows that needed time which photonic waves need to transmit information from a heart cell or any other controller cell to hemoglobin and then to cells, depend on the number of spinors, Unruh temperature, the separation distance between cells and acceleration of molecules.

When, one uses a mobile, its waves divide into smaller photons. Each photon interacts with spinors and cause a delay in transmission of information. We can write:

$$B_{mobile\ wave} = \sum_{x=1}^X B_{mobile,photon,x}$$

$$U_{i_1 \dots i_n} = \frac{[B_{i_1 \dots i_n} + B_{mobile,photon,x}]^2}{2\mu_0} = \frac{\lambda_{i_1 \dots i_n} [S_{i_1} + \dots + S_{i_n} + B_{mobile,photon,x}]^2}{2\mu_0}$$
(25)

Using above equation, we can repeat calculations in equations 12-24 and obtain the new time:

$$t_{bio-Photon,information,N+Mobile\ waves} =$$

$$\sum_{x=1}^X \sum_{n=1}^N t_{bio-Photon+mobile\ photons,x,i_1 \dots i_n} =$$

$$\sum_{x=1}^X \hat{P}_x \sum_{n=1}^N h \left[\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{E_{bio-Photon+mobile\ photons,x,i_1 \dots i_n}}{m} \otimes \right]$$

$$\prod_{n=1}^N \sum_{i_1 \dots i_n} \sqrt{\hat{P}_{i_1 \dots i_n, x} \left[\left[\frac{\tanh^m r_{T_{i_1 \dots i_n, x}}}{\cosh r_{T_{i_1 \dots i_n, x}}} \right]^2 \right]}^{-1}$$
(26)

Where \hat{P}_x is the probability for the interaction of photon x of mobile wave with the biological spinors. Above equation shows that mobile waves divide into x small photons which each photon interact with spinors and photons within the biological system. These interactions cause to a delay in transmission of information from a spinor on the hemoglobin or heart cells to other spinors on the normal cells. This delay causes that a cell acts independent of other cells and some types of diseases like tumors are emerged.

Discussions:

Biological spinors within the body, form an entangled system which transmits information from the heart to hemoglobin and cells. These spinors emit two types of waves including 1. Spinor waves and 2. Photons which their differences in needed time for transformation of information cause to the oscillation of heart cells and motions of blood cells including hemoglobin. A mobile wave with any wavelength includes some photons with smaller size than cells which break entanglement between biological spinors and causes to a delay in transmission of information and oxygen to cells. Without information and oxygen, cells have to do their affairs independent of biological system and use of respirational methods like the Warburg mechanism for tumor cells. Consequently, some tumor cells may be emerged which change the spinor structure to diagnose the place of T-cells and become ready for killing them. To prevent this event, by using mobile waves, one can induce some noises around tumor cells which cause to losing information. Consequently, T-cells have the opportunity to kill tumor cells. On the other hand, eventually, biological systems become resistance to mobile waves and the probability for production of tumor cells and other diseases decreases.

Conclusions: Up to date, it has been believed that most of mobile waves couldn't have any effect on cells. Because, their wavelengths are very bigger than the size of cells. However, wavelength is a quantum quantity which determines the probability for the existence of a photon in each point. The size of a photon itself is very smaller than the size of cells. Although, by reducing the wavelength, the probability for the existence of a photon in each point increases; however, even for radio waves with large wavelength, this probability isn't zero. In this research, we have shown that mobile waves break entanglements between spinors in a biological system like blood circularly one and produce new entanglements between them and electrons on mobile or tower antennas. A heart and hemoglobin molecules within blood cells are built from spinors which exchange information and are entangled. These spinors send or receive two types of waves. 1. Spinor waves which their velocity is infinite. This means that by any change in spin of one spinor in a pair, other spin changes immediately. 2. Photons which have limited velocities and could transform information after a period of time. For

example, suppose one of spinors in a pair sends some photons towards other spinor. Before reaching photons to second spinor, if the spin of first spin reverses, other spin changes fastly. However, photons have the memory of initial state and repel second spinor. By passing time, new photons are emerged which have true information. These photons reach the second spinor and attract them. These repels and attracts cause to oscillation of heart cells and motions of blood cells within vessels. These spinors transmit information and give it to cells. If a mobile wave achieve to heart and blood cells, divide into photons and each photon can break entanglements between spinors of heart and hemoglobin molecules and produce new entanglements between these spinors and those moving on the mobile antenna. This causes to information loss around cells. Some of cells couldn't obtain the needed information and act separately. Also, some hemoglobin molecules couldn't transmit oxygen to cells very good. Consequently, cells have to use of respirational methods which don't need to oxygen like those which are using by tumor cells in the Warburg proposal. This may cause to the cancer. According to the Warburg effect, tumor cells which are produced through this way, produce different number of spinors respect to normal cells. These spinors break some entanglements and could be diagnosed by T-cells. On the other hand, motion of T-cells cause to a change in spinors which could be diagnosed by tumor cells. These cells become ready to response by producing PD1/PD-L1 connections. To avoid of these connections, we can use of mobile waves to inject photons and new spinor states around tumor cells. These new photons and spinors play the role of noises around tumor cells. Consequently, tumor cells couldn't diagnose the existence of T-cells and these cells have the opportunity to kill them. Maybe, one asks that if mobile waves could cause to the cancer, why this couldn't observed within present human communities. To response, we should acknowledge that by passing time, biological spinors within biological system could be reprogramed to accept the existence of extra waves. However, if intensity or wavelengths change, again entangled spinors couldn't do their affairs and information transmission and new diseases are emerged.

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